

Detection process and accuracy of Intrusion Detection (ID) using machine learning

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Enhancing detection process and accuracy of Intrusion Detection (ID) using three machine-learning algorithms namely, BayesNet algorithm, Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). This was achieved by using a set of feature selection approaches Infogain (IG), ReleifF (RF), and Genetic Search (GS). This resulted in enhancing the classification performance with the GS accuracy rate is 99.9%. [1]

Several experiments using various machine-learning classifiers were done on KDD intrusion dataset. This was done with a focus on false negative and false positive performance metrics to enhance the detection rate of the intrusion detection system, resulting that decision table classifier achieved the lowest value of false negative while the random forest classifier has achieved the highest average accuracy rate. [2]

Denial of service is one of the most prevalent network attacks that need an effective approach to detect intrusion in the network using Management Information Base (MIB) database associated with the Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) through machine learning techniques. The impact of SNMP-MIB data on network anomalies detection using three classifiers, namely, Random Forest, AdaboostM1 and MLP to build the detection model, the use of machine learning techniques showed detecting and classifying the attacks with a high detection rate. [3]

Using the J48, MLP, and Bayes Network classifiers it was shown that J48 classifier has achieved the highest accuracy rate for detecting and classifying all KDD dataset attacks, which are of type DOS, R2L, U2R, and PROBE. [4]

Network domains are very complex structures, which leads to many faults in its communications leading to a poor quality of service. The use of Mobile Agents (MA) is a new technology based on mobile code that can migrate from one node

to another in order to collect, analyze and make decisions locally or remotely on behalf of a centralized network management station.[5]

Using Subset of Management Information Base (MIB) variables for change detection in network traffic using the most popular change detection online methods, showing advantages and disadvantages in addition to applications that use these methods such as network fault management, security management, and performance management.[6]

Over the years, network attacks have evolved into more complex and sophisticated methods for network intrusion. As network domains become bigger in terms of size, the number of external users increases and thus the systems become more open and subject to security threats.

Thus, the intrusion detection system was introduced to automatically detect network attacks.

Commercial solutions are generally centralized and suffer from scalability difficulties when applied in large networks. The use of distributed model scalability was eliminated. Mobile agent syndicates with statistical methods based on the Wiener filter to collect and analyze the network data to detect anomalous behavior. The algorithm was tested against four network attacks in both light and heavy traffic scenarios.[7]

Fault management is the main factor in availability of the network by proactively identifying faults and start the recovery process. Current network domains suffer from insufficient scalability, availability and flexibility due to its distribution. The analytical model for network management client/server (CS) and MA paradigms are used to build an analytical framework to quantitatively assess the performances of the MA and CS paradigms in different scenarios. This framework is based on a combination of MA and CS schemes called Adaptive Intelligent Mobile Agent.[8]

For Cloud Computing, Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) is the most serious attack that can cause a total deactivation of service. With the inability to be defended by traditional defense mechanisms, an anomaly intrusion detection approach in the hypervisor layer was introduced, using a neural network which integrates the particle swarm optimization with neural network for detection and classification of the traffic that is exchanged between virtual machines, leading to minimizing false alarms and high detection accuracy.[9]

Advance networks in term of size, application and complexity are sustainable to emerging attacks such as DDoS attacks. A hybrid approach is used to detect a DDoS attack by means of monitoring abnormal traffic in the network, the hybrid approach consists of traffic prediction and changing detection, combining these approaches, led to achieving a highly significant accuracy rate of 98.3% and sensitivity was 100%.[10]

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